

What can pictures still do in the 21st century? Figuring reality in visual arts Comment imager le XXI^e siècle? Figurer la réalité dans les arts visuels

International Conference (CLIMAS Bordeaux Montaigne University) 3-4 July 2025

Provisional program

Thursday, July 3rd – Site Pey Berland Université de Bordeaux, Place Pey Berland Bordeaux - Amphithéâtre ELLUL et salle RG

9h **Opening of the conference**

9h30 –11h **Embodied images in virtual worlds**

Fabrizia Bandi: “Image as Space: Perception, Presence, and Artistic Remediations in Virtual Reality”

Margherita Fontana: “Imagining the face of the “cave man”: Some cases of hyper-unrealism in Paleoart (but not only)”

Evi Roumani: “Images now: Performing the real”

11h-11h30 **Coffee break**

11h30 - 12h30 **KEYNOTE Maryse Ouellet:** “The Politics of Appearances: Why Art Matters in the Age of Digital Opacity”

12h45-14h15 **Lunch Break** (en ville)

14h30 –16h **Shifting visualities in figurative art**

Rachel Magdeburg: “First-Person Figures: Zombie Paintings in a New *Zeitgeist*”

Xavier Bourguine: “La Peinture 100 réels: copier, coller, rogner et fixer le monde à l’heure l’IA”

Andrés Franco Harnache: “Literary visuality in the age of AI: Ross Goodwin’s *1 the Road*”

16h-16h30 **Coffee break**

16h30-18h **(Re)Generating popular culture through digital iconography**

Ilan Manouach: “Generative Palimpsests: The Feature Space of Synthetic Comics”

Hui Wang: “Cartoon Art at the Turn of the Millenium: Art, Counterculture, Globality, and Metaverse of the Spectacle”

Louise Bouvet-Zieleskiewicz: “Figures virtuelles et réalités fuyantes: le cinéma vidéoludique de Pogg & Vinel face aux nouvelles images”

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19h30 / 20h

Dîner en ville

Friday, July 4th - Maison des Sciences Humaines de Bordeaux (MSH Bordeaux) – Domaine Universitaire PESSAC

9h-11h

Post-factual historical (counter)narratives

Louis Boulet: “Document reality or complicate it? Functions of figuration in Ahlam Shibli’s work”

Camille Rouquet: “Iconic Distortions: The Role of Historical Photographs in Shaping American Visual Identity”

Elpida Ziavra: “Figuring (out) the Human in the Photographic Portraits of Keisha Scarville’s *lick of tongue, rub of finger, on soft wound*”

11h-11h30

Coffee break

11h30 - 12h30

KEYNOTE Andrea Pinotti: “Self-Negating Images. An-Icons and the Promises of Virtuality”

12h30-14h

Lunch Break (traiteur à la MSH)

14h-15h30

Deconstructing or Reconstructing landscape photography?

Miles Jordan: “Visualizing Climate Change: Infrared Photography as a Tool for Reinterpreting Reality”

Rodrigo Fontanari: “Jouer avec la poéticité du monde: visions et simulations du monde à partir des travaux de Kevin Abosche”

Tanguy Gatay: “Ce que la virtualité fait au réel - à propos du travail de François Bellabas”

15h30-16h

Coffee break (si présence Jordan Miles)

16h-17h30

The Elusive transparency of contemporary cinema

Luca Tsingos: “Le De-Aging, lifting cinématographique”

Yosr Dridi: “Figuring Subjective Reality: Filmic-Photographic Minimalism and Raw Realism in Wim Wenders’s *Perfect Days* (2023)”

Conclusion of the conference